

The Interdependence of Man and Nature in the Process of Globalization

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 04 Aug 2024; **Accepted:** 04 Sep 2024; **Published:** 18 Oct 2024

Abstract: In the period of globalization, humanity is faced with a number of problems related to climate change. We should work together to address these alarming situations related to environmental change. We can prevent situations caused by climate change only if ecological culture and ecological literacy are formed in the population at a high level. For this, we need to start and develop the eco-movement in our republic and the world community. Protecting the flora and fauna, and delivering the living nature that surrounds us to the future generations in its original form shows that our ecological culture is high.

Keywords: philosophy, ontology, ecology, globalization, flora, fauna, climate change, healthy lifestyle.

In the course of today's globalization, the socio-economic development of mankind has radically changed. As a result of these changes, a number of urgent significant problems arose, the sphere of influence of which covered the world community, determined the future social progress of mankind. These problems are called global problems of mankind, and on the way to finding a solution, it is advisable to concentrate the strength and capabilities of all states

Currently, the practical importance of Ecology has sharply increased with the emergence of ecological crisis on the surface and the need to carry out conservation work on a large scale, as a result of the increased negative impact of man on the biosphere. An inextricable connection between ecology and Philosophy, Sociology, etc. has appeared between several disciplines. Currently, in the development of ways to solve industrial and agricultural production, transport, construction, scientific and technical, demographic problems and rational use of natural resources, ecological the approach has become necessary.

In order to reduce the impact of Global climate change, all of humanity must work in harmony. We can list the problems caused by climate change such as temperature rise, ozone depletion, forest shrinkage at present, increased carbon dioxide gas index in air, increased noise in cities, increased industrial emissions and daily emissions, pesticide damage of soils, Island problem, water pollution, increased effects of parnik effect. The ozone layer of the atmosphere is a shield that captures the sun's ultraviolet rays. Unfortunately, as a result of a natural imbalance on our planet, an environmental risk has appeared associated with the erosion of the ozone layer. This can lead to unpredictable changes in the climate in the future, that is, to a weakening of the immune system of the human body, an increase in the number of oncological diseases, slow growth of plants.

Gender equality is also important in addressing environmental issues. Representatives of both sexes are equally responsible for preventing problems in society. Environmental education it is necessary to start providing environmental education to the child from the family circle after the birth of the child.

Special environmental education places have been established in the picturesque resorts of nature in Germany. In them, in the summer months, specialist teachers improve their qualifications in Ecology, after returning to school, put into practice the knowledge gained, their experience. After all, raising children in the spirit of love for nature is not just a thing to do for a pastime. This is an urgent issue of state significance. Our future will be enlightened only if we raise and bring up healthy, hardworking, World-Wide young people. In this, the program organized for students their vacation time is achieved by obtaining interesting and useful climate knowledge.

The importance of organizing online classes on climate change. One effective way to increase the literacy of the population on climate change is to develop online programs. In doing so, participants will be free of transportation fees and accommodation fees to participate in the program. Of course, the topics in the program are organized by agreement, depending on the time of the participants. Participants can all participate, regardless of age, profession, social background and in what part of the world they are studying and working.

Together with the American embassy in Tashkent, the Climate change literacy program was formed. More than a hundred participants were elected in the program. The program was hosted by mentor-Abdulaziz Murtazoev. Online (zoom platform) classes were organized on 15 important topics on Global climate change.

In summary, in the Climate change literacy program, we have access to a wide range of information on what climate change is, what causes climate change to lead to, the various effects that occur as a result of the human factor, in which ways we can slow down climate change, the economical use of Natural Resources, the climate impact of energy use, international legal documents, One way to increase literacy in climate change is to organize similar online classes. There is no doubt that participants in the program will help to increase the knowledge of a wider population layer by sharing the knowledge they have gained from those around them. In addition, the use of various methods is also desirable in the formation of ecological culture. It is our duty to keep our mother planet one and together from different climate changes.

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